

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION 2 – FIGURES

TITLE: GAMMA/DELTA T CELL NEOPLASMS: HOW MANY AND HOW DIFFERENT?

Author: Margarida Lima

Figure S1. Flow cytometry studies in a peripheral blood sample from a healthy adult illustrating the main immunophenotypic features of the circulating $\alpha\beta$ and $\gamma\delta$ T cells.

Figure S1

Flow Cytometry:

Bivariate dot plots obtained by FCM analysis of the PB of a healthy adult, using the Infinicyt™ software, version 1.8.0 (Cytognos, Salamanca, Spain). Please note that although the percentage of $\gamma\delta$ Tc (red dots) are slightly increased (19.3% TC, 14.7% lymphocytes and 5.2% of the WBC in this PB sample), $\gamma\delta$ Tc are phenotypically heterogeneous, and they comprise both CD26-, CD27-, CD28- LGL, corresponding to CTL, and CD28+ non-LGL $\gamma\delta$ Tc (44% and 56% of $\gamma\delta$ Tc, respectively). In addition, as usually observed in the PB from healthy adults, the V δ 2+ $\gamma\delta$ Tc subset (66.4% of $\gamma\delta$ Tc), mostly paired with V δ 9 (76.4% of $\gamma\delta$ Tc), predominates over the V δ 1+ $\gamma\delta$ Tc subset (32.3% $\gamma\delta$ Tc). Normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc are represented as blue dots and other BM cells are represented as gray dots.

Peripheral blood cells were stained with 8-color combinations (FITC, PE, PC5.5, PC7, APC, APC-H7, V450, and KO) of mAbs specific for the antigens mentioned above. The specificities, clones, immunoglobulin isotypes and sources of the monoclonal antibodies used are listed at the end of this document. Cell surface staining was done using a stain-lyse-and-then-wash method, and the BD FACST™ Lysing Solution (Becton Dickinson), according to the instructions of the manufacturer. Intracellular staining was made using the Fix & Perm Cell Permeabilization Kit (Invitrogen), also according to the instructions of the manufacturer. Sample acquisition was performed in BD FACSCanto II™ flow cytometer. FSC and SSC, represented as FSC area and SSC area, were captured on a linear scale, and SSC was represented with a mathematic transformation to expand the values of the lower part of the scale for a better visualization of the populations (Exp-SSC-Low). For fluorescence parameters, a logarithmic amplification was used, with logical transformation. At least 200 000 cell events were recorded per tube and stored as flow cytometry standard (.fcs) 3.0 files for subsequent analysis.

Abbreviations: $\alpha\beta$ Tc, alpha/beta T cells; APC, Allophycocyanin; BM, bone marrow; CTL, cytotoxic T cells; $\gamma\delta$ Tc, gamma/delta T cells; LGL, large granular lymphocytes; PC5.5, PE-Cyanine 5.5; PC7, PE-Cyanine 7; FCM, Flow Cytometry; FITC, Fluorescein Isothiocyanate; FSC, Forward Scatter; KO, Krome orange; PB, peripheral blood; PE, Phycoerythrin; PMT, Photomultiplier tubes; SSC, Side Scatter; Tc, T cells; V450, Violet 450.

Figure S2

Flow Cytometry:

Bivariate dot plots obtained by FCM analysis of the PB from a patient with GDTLGLL, using the Infinicyt™ software, version 1.8.0 (Cytognos, Salamanca, Spain). Please note that $\gamma\delta$ Tc (red dots), which represent 42.0% TC, 31.3% lymphocytes and 10.5% of the WBC, are CD2+, CD3+, TCR- $\gamma\delta$ +, CD4-, CD5+low, CD7+, CD8-, CD11a+high, CD11b+, CD11c+, CD16+, CD26-, CD27-, CD28-, CD30-, CD38+, CD45RA+, CD45RO-, CD56+, CD57+, CD94+, CD158a+, CD158e1/NKB1-/+ (a few positive cells), CD161+, HLA-DR-, TiA1+, granzyme B+ and perforin+. In addition, most $\gamma\delta$ Tc were V δ 1-, V δ 2+, and V δ 9+. Normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc are represented as blue dots and other PB cells are represented as gray dots.

Sample processing, including cell staining and data acquisition, was performed as described in Figure 1 legend.

Clinical information: Female, 67 years old. Pancytopenia. PB counts - WBC $3.7 \times 10^9/l$; neutrophils 57.5%, lymphocytes 35.1%; monocytes 3.4%; Hg 11.7 g/dl; Platelets $95 \times 10^9/l$. 7

Abbreviations: $\alpha\beta$ Tc, alpha/beta T cells; APC, Allophycocyanin; FCM, Flow Cytometry; FITC, Fluorescein Isothiocyanate; FSC, Forward Scatter; $\gamma\delta$ Tc, gamma/delta T cells; PB, peripheral blood; PC5.5, PE-Cyanine 5.5; PC7, PE-Cyanine 7; SSC, Side Scatter; Tc, T cells; WBC, white blood cells; V450, Violet 450.

Figure S3. Flow cytometry studies in a peripheral blood sample from a patient with gamma-delta T cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia originating from V δ 1+/V γ 9- T cells.

Figure S3

Flow cytometry:

Bivariate dot plots obtained by FCM analysis of the PB a patient with GDTLGLL, using the Infinicyt™ software, version 1.8.0 (Cytognos, Salamanca, Spain. Please note that $\gamma\delta$ Tc (red dots), which represent 48.1% of the Tc, 43.5% of lymphocytes and 28.6% of the WBC, are CD2+, CD3+, TCR- $\gamma\delta$ +, CD4-, CD5-, CD7+, CD8-/+, CD11a+high, CD11b-, CD11c-, CD16-, CD26-, CD27+, CD28-, CD38+, CD45RA+, CD45RO-/+, CD56-, CD57+, HLA-DR+ (heterogeneous). In addition, most $\gamma\delta$ Tc are V δ 1+, V δ 2-, and V γ 9-. Normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc are represented as blue dots and other PB cells are represented as gray dots.

Sample processing, including cell staining and data acquisition, was performed as described in Figure 1.

Clinical information: Male, 69 years old. Rheumatoid arthritis. Severe neutropenia. PB counts – WBC $2.4 \times 10^9/l$; neutrophils: 0.5%, lymphocytes 65.4%; monocytes 32.5%; Hg 10.8 g/dl; Platelets: $220 \times 10^9/l$.

Abbreviations: $\alpha\beta$ Tc, alpha/beta T cells; APC, Allophycocyanin; FCM, Flow Cytometry; FITC, Fluorescein Isothiocyanate; FSC, Forward Scatter; $\gamma\delta$ Tc, gamma/delta T cells; GDTLGLL, gamma/delta T cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia; Hg, hemoglobin; KO, Krome orange; PB, peripheral blood; PC5.5, PE-Cyanine 5.5; PC7, PE-Cyanine 7; PE, Phycoerythrin; SSC, Side Scatter; Tc, T cells; WBC, white blood cells; V450, Violet 450.

Figure S4. Flow cytometry studies in a bone marrow sample from a patient with hepatosplenic gamma-delta T cell lymphoma originating from V δ 1+/V γ 9- T cells.

Figure S4

Flow cytometry:

Bivariate dot plots obtained by FCM analysis of the BM aspirate from a patient with HSGDTCL, using the Infinicyt™ software, version 1.8.0 (Cytognos, Salamanca, Spain). Please note that $\gamma\delta$ Tc (red dots), which represent 91% of Tc, 88% of the lymphoid cells and 38% of TNC in the BM, are CD2+, CD3+low, TCR- $\gamma\delta$ +, CD4-, CD5-/+low (25%), CD7+, CD8-, CD11a+low, CD11b+, CD11c+, CD16+, CD25-, CD26-, CD27+, CD28+,low, CD30-, CD38+, CD45RO+, CD56- (6%), CD57-, CD62L-, CD94+, CD158a+, CD158e1/NKB1-, CD161+, CD181/CXCR1-, CD195/CCR5-, CD197/CCR7-, HLA-DR-/+ (heterogeneous) (54%), TiA1-/+low, (74%), granzyme B- and perforin-. In addition, most $\gamma\delta$ Tc are V δ 1+, V δ 2-, and V γ 9-. Please note that HSGDTCL cells are considerably larger (FSC) and more complex (SSC) than the normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc, as well as than GDTLGLL cells (please compare with Figures 2 and 3). In the PB, the abnormal $\gamma\delta$ Tc represented 41% of Tc, 34.4% of lymphocytes (data not shown). Normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc are represented as blue dots and other BM cells are represented as gray dots.

Sample processing, including cell staining and data acquisition, was performed as described in Figure 1.

Clinical information: Male, 32 years old. Splenomegaly and pancytopenia. PB counts – WBC $3.0 \times 10^9/l$; neutrophils 57.0%, lymphocytes 28.7%; monocytes 12.8%; Hg 7.8 g/dl; Platelets: $45 \times 10^9/l$.

Abbreviations: $\alpha\beta$ Tc, alpha/beta T cells; APC, Allophycocyanin; BM, bone marrow; FCM, Flow Cytometry; FITC, Fluorescein Isothiocyanate; FSC, Forward Scatter; $\gamma\delta$ Tc, gamma/delta T cells; Hg, hemoglobin; KO, Krome orange; PB, peripheral blood; PE, Phycoerythrin; PC5.5, PE-Cyanine 5.5; PC7, PE-Cyanine 7; SSC, Side Scatter; Tc, T cells; TNC, total nucleated cells; WBC, white blood cells; V450, Violet 450.

Figure S5

Flow cytometry: Bivariate dot plots obtained by FCM analysis of the BM from a patient with celiac disease and EATCL diagnosed by histopathology, using the Infinicyt™ software, version 1.8.0 (Cytognos, Salamanca, Spain). Please note that $\gamma\delta$ Tc (red dots), which represent 89.5% of the Tc, 87.1% of the lymphoid cells and 27.8% of TNC in the BM, are large cells with the following immunophenotype: CD2+, CD3+, TCR- $\gamma\delta$ +, CD4-, CD5-, CD7+, CD8-, CD11a+high, CD11b-, CD11c+, CD16-, CD25-, CD26-, CD27-, CD28-, CD38+, CD45RA+low, CD56-, CD57-, CD94+low, CD158a-, CD158e1-, CD161+, HLA-DR+ (heterogeneous), granzyme B+ and perforin+. In addition, the abnormal $\gamma\delta$ Tc are V δ 1+, V δ 2- and V δ 9-. Please note that although IGDTCL cells had an immunophenotype indistinguishable from that usually observed in GDTLGLL, they are considerably larger (FSC) and more complex (SSC) than the normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc, as well as than GDTLGLL cells (please compare with Figures 2 and 3). Normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc are represented as blue dots and other cells are represented as gray dots.

Sample processing, including cell staining and data acquisition, was performed as described in Figure 1, except that 4-color staining was used instead of 8-color staining.

Clinical information: Female, 67 years old. Long term refractory diarrhea previously diagnosed as CD. PB counts – not available.

Abbreviations: $\alpha\beta$ Tc, alpha/beta T cells; APC, Allophycocyanin; BM, bone marrow; CD, Celiac disease; FCM, Flow Cytometry; FITC, Fluorescein Isothiocyanate; FSC, Forward Scatter; EATCL, enteropathy associated T cell lymphoma, gamma/delta subtype; $\gamma\delta$ Tc, gamma/delta T cells; Hg, hemoglobin; KO, Krome orange; LN, lymph node; PB, peripheral blood; PC5.5, PE-Cyanine 5.5; PC7, PE-Cyanine 7; PE, Phycoerythrin; SSC, Side Scatter; Tc, T cells; TNC, total nucleated cells; WBC, white blood cells; V450, Violet 450.

Figure S6. Flow cytometry studies in a lymph node biopsy (panel A) and a peripheral blood sample (panel B) from a patient with nodal gamma/delta T cell lymphoma originating from V δ 1+/V γ 9- T cells.

Figure S6

Flow cytometry:

Bivariate dot plots obtained by FCM analysis of the LN (panel A) and of the PB (panel B) from a patient with NGDTCL using the Infinicyt™ software, version 1.8.0 (Cytognos, Salamanca, Spain). Please note that $\gamma\delta$ Tc (red dots), which represent 98.1% of the Tc, 91.0% of the lymphoid cells and 90.0% of TNC in the LN, and 62.6% of the Tc, 43.2% of the lymphoid cells and 12.3% of the WBC in the PB, are CD2+, CD3+, TCR- $\gamma\delta$ +, CD4-, CD5+high, CD7-, CD8-, CD11b-, CD11c- (a few cells dimly positive), CD16-, CD25-/+ , CD28+high, CD30-, CD38-, CD45RA-, CD45RO+high, CD56-, CD57-, CD62L+, HLA-DR-/+ (heterogeneous). In addition, the abnormal $\gamma\delta$ Tc are V γ 9+ and V δ 2+ (data not shown). Normal residual $\alpha\beta$ Tc are represented as blue dots and other cells are represented as gray dots.

Sample processing, including cell staining and data acquisition, was performed as described in Figure 1, except that 3-color staining was used instead of 8-color staining and a FACSCalibur™ flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson) was used instead of a FACSCantoII.

Clinical information: Female, 45 years old. One-month history of cervical lymphadenopathy and one-week history of skin lesions. Physical examination: Large mandibular and parotid adenopathy, skin lesions and eosinophilia. PB counts: WBC $15.9 \times 10^9/L$; neutrophils 57%; lymphocytes 13.0%; eosinophils 28.0%; Hg 15.3 g/dl; platelets $286 \times 10^9/l$. Evolution: The patient was successively treated with various schemas of combined chemotherapy without response, dying 4 months after diagnosis with sepsis, thrombosis of the axillary and subclavian veins and disease progression. This case was previously published [214].

Abbreviations: $\alpha\beta$ Tc, alpha/beta T cells; APC, Allophycocyanin; FCM, Flow Cytometry; FITC, Fluorescein Isothiocyanate; FSC, Forward Scatter; $\gamma\delta$ Tc, gamma/delta T cells; Hg, hemoglobin; KO, Krome orange; LN, lymph node; NGDTCL, nodal gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; PB, peripheral blood; PC5.5, PE-Cyanine 5.5; PC7, PE-Cyanine 7; PE, Phycoerythrin; SSC, Side Scatter; Tc, T cells; TNC, total nucleated cells; WBC, white blood cells; V450, Violet 450.

Specificities, clones, immunoglobulin isotypes and sources of the monoclonal antibodies used in 8-color protocols.

Specificities ¹	Clones	Isotypes	Conjugates ²	Sources ³
CD1a	BL6	IgG1	APC	IOT
CD2	SFCI3Pt2H9	IgG1	FITC	BC
CD3	SK7	IgG1	APC-H7	BDB
CD4	RPA-T4	IgG1	HV450	BDH
CD5	L17F12	IgG2a	APC	BDB
CD7	3A1E-12H7	IgG2b	PE	BC
CD8	B9.11	IgG1	KO	IOT
CD10	HI10a	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD11a	CLB-LFA-1/2,TB-133	IgG2a	FITC	CLB
CD11a	LFA-1	IgG2a	FITC	BDPH
CD11b	D12	IgG2a	APC	BDB
CD11c	S-HCL-3	IgG2a	APC	BDB
CD16	3G8	IgG1	FITC	IOT
CD25	2A3	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD26	BA5	IgG2a	PE	IOT
CD27	CLB-CD27/1,9F4	IgG2a	FITC	CLB
CD27	M-T721	IgG1	FITC	BDB
CD28	CD28.2	IgG1	PC7	IOT
CD30	HRS4	IgG1	APC	IOT
CD31	1F11	IgG1	PE	IOT
CD38	HB7	IgG1	APC	BDB
CD45	J.33	IgG1	KO	IOT
CD45RA	L48	IgG1	FITC	BDB
CD45RO	UCHL-1	IgG2a	PE	BDB
CD56	NCAM16.2	IgG2b	PE	BDB
CD57	HNK-1	IgM	FITC	BDB
CD62L	REG56	IgG1	APC	IOT
CD94	HP-3D9	IgG1	APC	BDPH
CD103	2G5	IgG2a	FITC	IOT
CD158a	HP-3E4	IgM	FITC	BDB
CD158b	CH-L	IgG2b	PE	BDPH
CD158e1 (NKB1)	DX9	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD181 (CXCR1)	5A12	IgG2b	FITC	BDPH
CD183 (CXCR3)	1C6/CXCR3	IgG1	APC	BDPH
CD185 (CXCR5)	MU5UBEE	IgG2b	FITC	EBIO
CD195 (CCR5)	2D7/CCR5	IgG2a	PE	BDPH
CD197 (CCR7)	150503	IgG2a	PE	R&D

¹ CD, Cluster of Differentiation; HLA, Human Leukocyte Antigens; TCR, T cell Receptor

² FITC, Fluorescein isothiocyanate; PE, Phycoerythrin; PerCP, Peridinin-Chlorophyll-Protein complex; PC5.5, PE-Cyanine 5.5; PC7, PE-Cyanine 7; APC, Allophycocyanin; APC-H7, Allophycocyanin-H7; KO, Krome orange; PB, Pacific Blue

³ BC, Beckman Coulter, Miami, FL, USA; BDB, Becton Dickinson Biosciences, San José, CA, USA; BDH, Becton Dickinson Horizon, San José, CA, USA; BDPH, Becton Dickinson Pharmingen, San José, CA, USA; BIOL, Biolegend; CLB, Amsterdam, The Netherlands; E-BIO, E-Bioscience IOT, Immunotech, Marseille, France; PH, Pharmingen, San Diego, CA, USA

Specificities, clones, immunoglobulin isotypes and sources of the monoclonal antibodies used in 8-color protocols.

Specificities ¹	Clones	Isotypes	Conjugates ²	Sources ³
CD161	DX12	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD279	PD1.3	IgG2b	APC	IOT
Granzyme B	GB11	IgG1	PB	BIOL
Granzyme B	GB11	IgG1	V450	BDH
HLA-DR	L243 (G46-6)	IgG2a	PE	BDB
Perforin	dG9	IgG2b	FITC	BDB
TCL-1	eBio1-21	IgG2b	APC	EBIO
TCR- $\alpha\beta$	T10B9.1A-31	IgM	FITC	PH
TCR- $\gamma\delta$	IMMU510	IgG1	PC5.5	IOT
TiA1	2G9	IgG1	PE	IOT

Specificities, clones, immunoglobulin isotypes and sources of the monoclonal antibodies used in 4-color protocols.

Specificities ⁴	Clones	Isotypes	Conjugates ⁵	Sources ⁶
CD2	SFCI3Pt2H9	IgG1	FITC	BC
CD3	SK7	IgG1	APC	BDB
CD4	13B8.2	IgG1	FITC	IOT
CD4	SK3	IgG1	PERCP	BDB
CD5	L17F12	IgG2a	PE	BDB
CD7	3A1E-12H7	IgG2b	PE	BC
CD8	B9.11	IgG1	FITC	IOT
CD8	SK1	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD11a	CLB-LFA-1/2,TB-133	IgG2a	FITC	CLB
CD11a	G-25.2	IgG2a	FITC	BDB
CD11b	D12	IgG2a	PE	BDB
CD11c	S-HCL-3	IgG2a	PE	BDB
CD16	3G8	IgG1	FITC, PE	IOT
CD25	2A3	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD26	BA5	IgG2a	PE	IOT
CD27	CLB-CD27/1,9F4	IgG2a	FITC	CLB
CD28	L293	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD34	8G12	IgG1	APC, FITC	BDB
CD38	HB7	IgG1	FITC	BDB
CD45	2D1	IgG1	PERCP	BDB
CD45RA	L48	IgG1	FITC	BDB
CD45RO	UCHL-1	IgG2a	PE	BDB
CD56	N901 (NKH-1)	IgG1	FITC, PE, PC5	IOT
CD57	HNK-1	IgM	FITC	BDB
CD94	HP-3D9	IgG1	FITC	BDPH
CD122	MIK-b	IgG2a	FITC	CLB
CD158a	HP-3E4	IgM	FITC	BDB
CD158b	CH-L	IgG2b	PE	BDPH
CD158e1 (NKB1)	DX9	IgG1	PE	BDB
CD161	DX12	IgG1	PE	BDB
HLA-DR	L243 (G46-6)	IgG2a	PE	BDB
TCR- $\alpha\beta$	T10B9.1A-31	IgM	FITC	BDPH
TCR- $\gamma\delta$	B1	IgG1	APC	BDPH

⁴ CD, Cluster of Differentiation; HLA, Human Leukocyte Antigens; TCR, T cell Receptor

⁵ FITC, Fluorescein isothiocyanate; PE, Phycoerythrin; PerCP, Peridinin-Chlorophyll-Protein complex; PC5, Phycoerythrin-Cy5 tandem; APC, Allophycocyanin

⁶ BC, Beckman Coulter, Miami, FL, USA; BDB, Becton Dickinson Biosciences, San José, CA, USA; CLB, Amsterdam, The Netherlands; IOT, Immunotech, Marseille, France; PH, Pharmingen, San Diego, CA, USA.